

BIR O'LCHAMLI PANJARADAGI SONI IKKIDAN OSHMAYDIGAN ZARRACHALAR SISTEMASIGA MOS, S-D ALMASHINISH MODELINING MUHIM SPEKTRI

A.Boltayev¹, Ch.Nurmurodova²

¹Sharof Rashidov nomidagi Samarqand davlat Universiteti], O'zbekiston

²Sharof Rashidov nomidagi Samarqand davlat Universiteti Matematika fakulteti 1-bosqich magistranti, O'zbekiston

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20266602>

Friedrichs modeli [1] va uning umumlashmalari ko'plab ishlarda o'rganilgan [3, 4]. Xususan, [5] ishida $\mathbb{C} \oplus L^2(\mathbb{T}^2)$ fazosida aniqlangan matritsa Hamiltonianining spektral xossalari batafsil tahlil qilingan.

$\mathbb{T} = (-\pi, \pi]$ bir o'lchamli tor bo'lsin.

Har bir $k \in \mathbb{T}$ uchun

$$(H_0(k)f)(p) = E_k(p)f(p), \quad E_k(p) = 2\left(1 - \cos\frac{k}{2}\cos p\right) - AS, \quad S > 0,$$

va

$$(Vf)(p) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{T}} f(t) dt$$

$E: \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, $Ef_0 = E_0f_0$, bu yerda $E_0 \in \mathbb{R}$ ichki energiya darajasi. Bog'lanish operatorlari:

$$C: \mathbb{C} \rightarrow L^2(\mathbb{T}), \quad (Cf_0)(p) = -\frac{A}{2}\sqrt{2S}f_0, \quad C^*: L^2(\mathbb{T}) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}, \quad C^*f_1 = -\frac{A}{2}\sqrt{2S} \int_{\mathbb{T}} f_1(t) dt.$$

$\mathcal{H} = \mathbb{C} \oplus L^2(\mathbb{T})$ fazosida operator quyidagi matritsa ko'rinishida berilgan:

$$H_A(k) = \begin{pmatrix} E & C^* \\ C & H_0(k) + \frac{A}{2}V \end{pmatrix},$$

$A < 0$ bog'lanish konstantasi.

Asosiy natijani bayon etishdan oldin qo'shimcha operatorning muhim xossasini ko'rsatamiz.

Lemma 1 $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & C^* \\ C & \frac{A}{2}V \end{pmatrix}$ operatorining rangi ikkiga teng bo'ladi.

Endi asosiy teoremani bayon etamiz.

Teorema 1 Har bir $k \in \mathbb{T}$ uchun

$$\sigma_{\text{ess}}(H_A(k)) = [E_{\min}(k), E_{\max}(k)],$$

bu yerda

$$E_{\min}(k) := \min_{p \in \mathbb{T}} E_k(p) = 2\left(1 - \cos\frac{k}{2}\right) - AS, \quad E_{\max}(k) := \max_{p \in \mathbb{T}} E_k(p) \\ = 2\left(1 + \cos\frac{k}{2}\right) - AS.$$

References

- [1] K. O. Friedrichs, *On the perturbation of continuous spectra*, Comm. Pure Appl. Math. **1** (1948), 361–406.
- [2] M. Reed, B. Simon, *Methods of Modern Mathematical Physics. IV: Analysis of Operators*, Academic Press, New York, 1978.
- [3] S. N. Lakaev, I. N. Bozorov, *The number of bound states of a one-particle Hamiltonian on a three-dimensional lattice*, Theoret. and Math. Phys. **158** (2009), 360–376.
- [4] S. N. Lakaev, Sh. Yu. Kholmatov, Sh. I. Khamidov, *Bose-Hubbard model with on-site and nearest-neighbor interactions; exactly solvable case*, J. Phys. A: Math. Theor. **54** (2021), 245201.
- [5] S. N. Lakaev, Sh. M. Latipov, *Two-Fermion Lattice Hamiltonian with First and Second Nearest-Neighboring-Site Interactions*, 2023.